

BASIC PRINCIPLES FOR DEVELOPING STATISTICAL ANALYSIS COMPETENCIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15161688>

Abstract. *The development of statistical analysis competencies in modern education helps to develop students' analytical thinking, independent thinking, making them capable of leading the country on the path of innovative development, equal among their peers in the world, knowledgeable and patriotic individuals. This article discusses the main principles that ensure the effective development of statistical analysis competencies. The main principles such as scientific approach, systematicity, practice-oriented education, interactivity and individualization are highlighted. Also, modern software tools such as Excel, SPSS and Python develop students' statistical skills. The results of the study show that relying on these principles helps to significantly increase students' ability to analyze data and apply statistical methods in practice.*

Keywords: *competencies, statistical analysis, scientific approach, interactivity, data analysis, seasonality, index.*

Introduction

The development of humanity and the increasing need for statistical information have led to the need to centralize statistics. The increasing use of data-based decision-making in the 21st century has further increased the importance of students developing strong statistical analysis competencies. These competencies are important not only for researchers, but also for professionals in various fields. Effective acquisition of statistical skills allows students to collect, analyze and interpret data, which is important for solving real-world problems. This article outlines the basic principles that ensure the development of statistical analysis competencies. By adhering to these principles, teachers can create a foundation for students to deeply understand and apply statistical methods in practice.

Statistical analysis competencies include a set of knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for conducting data-driven research. It is important to develop competencies such as analytical thinking, informed decision-making, and scientific research skills. The principle of the scientific approach introduces students to the theoretical foundations of statistical methods.

Methodology

Statistical knowledge should be delivered in a gradual and systematic manner. This principle includes the following:

- Introduce basic concepts before moving on to more advanced analysis techniques.
- Teach data collection, cleaning, analysis and interpretation as interrelated steps.
- Reinforce knowledge through regular repetition of specific concepts.

Statistical analysis competencies can be studied based on their importance and principles.

Based on these principles, we can statistically analyze the issues we encounter in our lives. We know that the production and consumption of certain products depend on the season. For example, the consumption of meat products is much higher in winter months, the consumption of thermal energy is much lower in summer months than in winter, the consumption of agricultural

products and especially their processing are also seasonal. Take the prices of products at the farmers' market, in some months their prices are 3-4 times more expensive than in the off-season months.

First, when drawing up a business plan, manufacturers know which months have the highest demand for the products produced by this enterprise. Secondly, entrepreneurs prepare to purchase agricultural products and store them during the winter months. Thirdly, when drawing up plans at the macroeconomic level (especially on investment issues), attention is paid to the development prospects of sectors. Fourthly and most importantly, natural and unnatural losses are reduced when delivering grown products (we are referring more to agricultural products) to consumers.

Results and discussion. Therefore, based on the above arguments, studying and measuring seasonality is one of the most important tasks in analyzing dynamic series.

Study and measure seasonality.

1. Seasonality index. In general, this index is determined by the ratio of the terms (Y_i) calculated based on the initial data (empirical) of the dynamic series to the theoretical term $:\bar{Y}$

$$J_M = \frac{Y_i}{\bar{Y}} * 100$$

here: J_M – seasonality index; Y_i – monthly initial data; average monthly level, i.e. $\bar{Y} = \sum Y_i : n$.

Grocery store turnover (million soums)

Months	Years.		
	2023	2024	2025
January	178	183	95
February	109	179	176
March	181	184	184
April	174	185	184
May	202	208	211
June	201	192	200
July	181	175	183

August	186	186	180
September	177	178	176
October	173	173	187
November	171	184	174
December	183	167	121
Total	2116	2194	2071
Average	176.3	182.8	172.6

This index, calculated by months of the year, is very unreliable in determining the regularity of fluctuations, since the influence of random factors can be high. Therefore, in statistics, this index is usually calculated based on three (at least) annual data. To calculate the seasonality index, we perform the following calculations. Based on the data provided for the grocery store in the table above, we calculate the average annual level for each month (Y_i):

$$\bar{Y}_i = \sum Y_i : n .$$

We calculate the seasonality index

Months	Three annual ($\sum U_i$)	An average of one annual ($\bar{Y}_i = \sum U_i$)	Seasonality index,% (J_M)
January	336	152.0	85.8
February	584	154.7	87.3
March	349	183.0	103.3
April	643	181.0	102.1
May	621	207.0	116.8
June	693	197.7	111.6
July	539	179.7	101.4
August	552	184.0	103.8
September	531	177.0	99.9
October	533	177.7	100.3
November	529	176.3	99.5
December	471	157.0	88.6
Total	6381	177.2	100.0

Million sums for January $\bar{Y}_i = \frac{178+183+95}{3} = \frac{456}{3} = 152,0$.

For February $\bar{Y}_i = \frac{109+179+176}{3} = \frac{464}{3} = 154,7$, million sums and soon.

Now the average monthly level is determined for all months together (\bar{Y}).

Let's calculate $= \frac{\sum Y_i}{36}$ in our example : \bar{Y}

1. $\bar{Y}=177.2$ million sums

2. $\bar{Y} = \frac{\sum Y_i}{12} = \frac{152,0+154,7+183,0+181,0+207,0+197,7}{12} +$

$$+ \frac{179,7+184,0+177,0+176,3+157,0}{12} = \frac{2127,1}{12} = 177,2 \text{ . sum.}$$

Average level (177.2) calculated for all months is used as a fixed base of comparison when determining the seasonality index. We calculate the seasonality index as follows:

January Thu=($Y_i : Y$)•100=(152.0:177.2)•100=85.8%

February Fri=(154.7:177.2)•100=87.3 % etc.

Seasonal fluctuations in grocery store sales

Average seasonality index. This index is calculated as follows. Seasonality indices are calculated for each year.

For example, for 2024: January $J_m = (95:172.6) \cdot 100 = 55.0\%$; February 102% $(176:172.6) \cdot 100$ average seasonality indices for each month of 2023-2025 .

$$\text{January} \quad \frac{101 + 100.1 + 55.0}{3} = \frac{256.1}{3} = 85.4 \%$$

$$\text{February} \quad \frac{61.8 + 97.9 + 102.0}{3} = \frac{261.7}{3} = 87.2 \%$$

$$\text{March} \quad \frac{102.7 + 100.7 + 106.6}{3} = \frac{310.0}{3} = 103.3 \% \text{ x . } k .$$

Calculating the average seasonality index at a grocery store

Months	by year , %.			Average seasonality index, %
	2023	2024.	2025	
January	101.0	100.1	55.0	85.4
February	61.8	97.9	102.0	87.2
March	102.7	100.7	106.6	103.3
April	98.7	101.2	106.6	102.2
May	114.6	113.8	122.2	116.9
June	114.0	105.0	115.9	111.6
July	102.7	95.7	106.0	101.5

August	105.5	101.8	104.3	103.9
September	100.4	97.4	102.0	99.3
October	98.1	94.6	108.3	100.3
November	97.0	100.7	100.8	99.5
December	103.8	91.4	70.1	88.4

Seen from the data presented in the above tables, the seasonality indices are almost the same. This means that the monthly levels for different years are relatively flat. If we carefully observe the seasonality indices presented in both tables, the development trend in the second method is more clearly visible. Based on the monthly ratios calculated in this way; it is also possible to determine the monthly actual data by the ratio of the moving average or the smoothed terms. Such examples are encountered throughout our lives. Statistical analysis of such problems develops students' statistical competencies.

Conclusion

Developing statistical analysis competencies helps students develop data-based thinking. It is important to be based on systematic principles. Basic principles such as the scientific approach, systematic teaching, practice-oriented education, interactivity and individualization form the ability to conduct statistical analysis. Students are motivated to gain in-depth knowledge and conduct scientific research based on accurate data. They gain an understanding of collecting data and conducting statistical analysis on the collected data. In addition, they learn to solve problems encountered in everyday life. As a result of statistical observation of a phenomenon using statistical analysis, students collect a wide range of information about it. It is not yet possible to make any conclusions based on this information, because it is scattered and diverse. Therefore, it consists in bringing the collected information into a single system, organizing it, and summarizing it. This problem is solved by statistical analysis.

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